

*Polifonia: a digital harmoniser for musical heritage knowledge,
H2020*

D6.5 Policy Recommendations, version 1.0

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Project information

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POLIFONIA consortium

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2	OU	THE OPEN UNIVERSITY	United Kingdom
3	KCL	KING'S COLLEGE LONDON	United Kingdom
4	NUI GALWAY	NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF IRELAND GALWAY	Ireland
5	MiC	MINISTERO DELLA CULTURA	Italy

6	CNRS	CENTRE NATIONAL DE LA RECHERCHE SCIENTIFIQUE CNRS	France
	SORBONN E	SORBONNE UNIVERSITE (LinkedTP)	France
7	CNAM	CONSERVATOIRE NATIONAL DES ARTS ET METIERS	France
8	NISV	STICHTING NEDERLANDS INSTITUUT VOOR BEELD EN GELUID	Netherlands
9	KNAW	KONINKLIJKE NEDERLANDSE AKADEMIE VAN WETENSCHAPPEN	Netherlands
10	DP	DIGITAL PATHS SRL	Italy

Project Summary

European musical heritage is a dynamic historical flow of experiences, leaving heterogeneous traces that are difficult to capture, connect, access, interpret, and valorise. Computing technologies have the potential to shed a light on this wealth of resources by extracting, materialising and linking new knowledge from heterogeneous sources, hence revealing facts and experiences from hidden voices of the past. Polifonia makes this happen by building novel ways of inspecting, representing, and interacting with digital content. Memory institutions, scholars, and citizens will be able to navigate, explore, and discover multiple perspectives and stories about European Musical Heritage.

Polifonia focuses on European Musical Heritage, intended as musical contents and artefacts - or music objects - (tunes, scores, melodies, notations, etc.) along with relevant knowledge about them such as: their links to tangible objects (theatres, conservatoires, churches, etc.), their cultural and historical contexts, opinions and stories told by people having diverse social and artistic roles (scholars, writers, students, intellectuals, musicians, politicians, journalists, etc.), and facts expressed in different styles and disciplines (memoires, reportage, news, biographies, reviews), different languages (English, Italian, French, Spanish, and German), and across centuries.

The overall goal of the project is to realise an ecosystem of computational methods and tools supporting discovery, extraction, encoding, interlinking, classification, exploration of, and access to, musical heritage knowledge on the Web. An equally important objective is to demonstrate that these tools improve the state of the art of Social Science and Humanities (SSH) methodologies. Hence their development is guided by, and continuously intertwined with, experiments and validations performed in real-world settings, identified by musical heritage stakeholders (both belonging to the Consortium and external supporters) such as cultural institutes and collection owners, historians of music, anthropologists and ethnomusicologists, linguists, etc.

Executive summary

The policy recommendations in this deliverable are based on the results and lessons learned in the Polifonia project. This report identifies areas of policy that affect the efficiency and quality of work that can be done by initiatives that engage with and promote European musical heritage. Its purpose is to inform and engage with policy makers at various levels to address issues relevant to Polifonia's work. We structure the policy recommendations in accordance with the FAIR principles, which ensure that data is Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable. This way, we emphasise the role of policy in creating awareness and a framework to execute research in a FAIR way. Similar to the Data management planning, which extends the management of Data towards the management of Data in context (as described in the Data Management Plan version 3, currently under approval), our policy actions are driven by Open Science and FAIR principles. The Final Policy Recommendations are written prior to the delivery of the Polifonia Web Portal and in parallel with other Deliverables/reports which address impact and re-usability of Polifonia results. Where appropriate we refer to those other papers.

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1. Introduction

1.1 Purpose of deliverable

If one thing has become apparent during the pandemic, it's the notion that digital engagement in society is still developing. People's experiences have been more confined to digital, online spaces and their interactions with cultural heritage have followed suit. The Polifonia project brings providers of cultural heritage content together with musicological scholars and computer scientists working on new web-based infrastructures. The project itself (starting 2021) in the first two years was affected by the restriction of the pandemic, this gave the project an extra boost to think about how to embrace the opportunities of digital and web technologies, if it comes to the engagement with cultural heritage - be it academic or mundane. As researchers and curators, we believe that our cultural heritage is both a reflection of values in society and a means to critically reflect on those values. It is also a source of beauty and entertainment and we have a responsibility to engage with people wherever they are. It has become paramount to improve the online presence of (in this case) musical cultural heritage: to organise our collections, datasets and research results in such a way that they can be retrieved, interpreted and reused.

This report identifies areas of policy that affect the efficiency and quality of work that can be done by initiatives that engage with and promote European musical heritage. It builds on our experiences with the variety of institutions which build the Polifonia consortium, their engagement policy and outreach and dissemination workflows, and what we created in the project to reach beyond Polifonia. Logically, this deliverable is placed in work package six, which concerns itself with dissemination and engagement aspects of Polifonia. The purpose of this deliverable is two-fold. First, it gives a summary of those Polifonia results which might be of interest for a wider audience. Second, it summarises our own lessons learned in the journey of engaging with various stakeholders. This way, we want to enable other projects and policy makers in the area of cultural heritage to learn about and build on our experiences. The Polifonia project consortium is especially concerned with connecting and enriching objects of musical heritage and this document will therefore address issues that relate to the activities of publishing data about musical heritage. However, some of the means with which we engaged stakeholders and the wider audience, are generic and possibly applicable also to other cultural heritage content.

This final policy brief provides a summary of the project's results and lessons learned by all partners. Based on the project's experiences, it provides recommendations aimed at policy makers that work for organisations managing and publishing heritage data and the organisations that are responsible for regulation in these areas. This includes, but is not limited to, policy makers at cultural institutions, people involved with research data management in universities, but also people in the political sphere that can influence the agenda of ministries of culture and legal experts that are involved with broadening possibilities for research of and engagement with cultural heritage.

1.2 Project set up

The work in Polifonia is mostly organised around ten pilots, which drive the development of the ecosystem through continuous validation of its technologies. These pilots address various topics related to improving access to musical cultural heritage. An overview of these pilots can be found in table 1 below.

Preserving musical heritage through knowledge graphs			https://polifonia-project.eu
1	BELLS	Preservation of Historical Bell Heritage: dependencies between tangible and intangible	
2	ORGANS	A Knowledge Graph on History of Pipe Organs	
Managing musical heritage collections through knowledge graphs			
3	FACETS	Exploration of music scores collections through statistical features	
4	INTERLINK	Interlinking of collections in digital music libraries and audiovisual archives	
Studying musical heritage through (interlinked) knowledge graphs			
5	CHILD	Exploration of musical heritage for scholarly enquiry: a case study on Music and Childhood.	
6	MUSICBO	Knowledge graph of Bologna Musical Heritage.	
7	TUNES	Tunes analysis and classification	
8	TONALITIES	Modal and tonal classification of Western notated music from the Renaissance to the 20th century	

Interacting with musical heritage knowledge graphs			
9	ACCESS	Making musical performances accessible to people who are Deaf or hearing impaired	
10	MEETUPS	Musical Meetups: the European musicianship flow	

Table 1: Polifonia’s 10 Pilots: Label and description, Icon and Grouping¹

2. Project results and lessons learned

2.1 General project findings

We list in this section some of the main project results. Those are partly research output (such as the Polifonia Research Ecosystem, The Polifonia Ontology Network), partly activities (such as Ensuring FAIRness, Governance principles, and Ensuring Impact).

Polifonia

Research

Ecosystem

The Polifonia Research Ecosystem represents the Polifonia approach to data management. It is aligned with other project knowledge management instruments such as Survey’s, Maninpasta (workshops), and supervised by the Technical Board. The Polifonia Research Ecosystem represents machine executable data (and other research components) management. It is both stable and flexible. Its stability is attributed to the formal (machine-actionable) documentation of components, such as the annotation scheme, and the establishment of defined workflows for annotating and selecting specific research assets as components. On the other hand, its flexibility arises from the ability to modify the annotation scheme and adapt the workflows for annotation, selection, and validation. The Polifonia Data Management Plan (D7.3) features an extensive overview of the components of the Polifonia Research Ecosystem.² The Polifonia Research Ecosystem design and implementation is the main foundation for FAIRness in the project and beyond. The approach behind the Ecosystem is available to future EU projects via the Research Ecosystem Framework (REECO), which incorporates all technologies and methods applied in Polifonia: the annotation scheme, the annotations scheme validator, and the website builder. More details can be found in Deliverable 5.7 – Tools for annotation and citation of musical scholarly objects (Daga, Enrico et al. 2023).

¹ For more detailed descriptions see Admiraal et al., Polifonia Deliverable 7.1 Data Management Plan. 2021.

² Polifonia Deliverable 7.3 Research Data Management Plan.

- Changes in the Deliverable template to add (1) a free text FAIR-section and (2) a checklist on FAIRness of components³ reported about in deliverables.

Governance

principles

Seeds for good open science lie already in the making of the project. One advantage stemming from the structure of the Polifonia project is its consortium, comprising not only research institutions but also institutions responsible for providing important content, including both knowledge and cultural heritage institutions. Although Polifonia is an innovative research project, in its consortium we find cultural heritage institutions and research infrastructure institutions such as Istituto Centrale Catalogo Documentazione (ICCD), the Netherlands Institute for Sound & Vision (NISV), Conservatoire national des arts et métiers (CNAM), DANS-KNAW and Meertens-KNAW. These institutions come with their own established data curation practices. Results produced in Polifonia sometimes directly lead to enrichment of metadata in resources provided by those institutions (see example below from the DMP v3); sometimes it contributes to training of those involved in further curating the content and providing interfaces - even if results not always immediately travel to the original production system. The existing data curation practices in the cultural heritage domain have informed Polifonia and the other way around. The networks of those institutions have also contributed to the formation of the Stakeholder Network - next to an open call for participation. Last but not least, many enrichments of data and new tooling will be preserved in the long-run by becoming part of those stable infrastructural institutions.

Example 1: Bells Ontology⁴

The BELLS ONTOLOGY is a result of Polifonia and is annotated as a component in the Polifonia Ecosystem. On the Website summary of the Bells Ontology is listed (<https://polifonia-project.github.io/ecosystem/polifonia-project/bells-ontology/header.html#bells-ontology>). When clicking on the 'Metadata' button on the Ecosystem website, the whole of the annotations for this component becomes visible. Scrolling through the metadata shows not only who produced this component, as part of which work package, but also explicitly notes on which other work it builds, which sources it reuses, and which licence it uses.

In the case of the Bells Ontology it becomes obvious that this ontology is a part of the overall Polifonia Ontology, while at the same time it also builds on an existing ontology which has been used for main source of the Bells pilot, namely the Catalogo generale dei Beni Culturali. This catalog was already published as Linked Data, but has now been enriched due to the work of the Polifonia project. The question of sustaining the work of Polifonia beyond the horizon of this project is addressed by the collaboration with a Cultural Heritage provider. The ICCD (Istituto Centrale per il Catalogo e la Documentazione) has enhanced the

³ Components means here 'components of the research ecosystem' which are of the types: Data, Tools, and Reports. They can be inspected here: <https://polifonia-project.github.io/ecosystem/> (see also Daga et al. 2023).

⁴ Section copied from Data Management Plan version 3

search functionalities of the catalog. Such impact and sustainability of Polifonia results relying on the construction of the consortium itself, can be found in many pilots.

Strategies for Impact and Re-Use

If we talk about Impact we can usually distinguish between Impact for the academic system itself (scientific or research impact), and Impact beyond (societal, economical, cultural). All European research projects come with a defined impact strategy. Although there is a high awareness of future impact, impact is also notoriously hard to be measured (Reale et al. 2017, pp. 298). As a consequence *Impact* is often traced in forms of narratives of those involved. Another problem is that impact shows itself often in an unexpected way, implicit and in the long-term. Having stated these known problems around impact, Polifonia has not hid away from this problem, but became and still is acting proactively.

Concerning the scientific impact Polifonia ensured a good knowledge flow across the various disciplines involved (from computer sciences, over musicology, to information sciences). To train in particular the earlier career researchers in interdisciplinary work was one of the main emphasis. The already interconnected networked structure of the project, where WP's (representing methodological areas) were connected via Pilots (representing use cases) was again and again additionally disturbed by pop-up workshops (Manin pasta) on issues of publishing linked data, programming interfaces, evaluation criteria, determine and annotating important research components. This led to many deliverables with larger author groups and many institutions involved. The Ecosystem as part of the DMP and the Zenodo community are the basis for a good documentation of scientific results.⁵ Polifonia's aspirations even push the boundaries of good Open Science principles. As described in the DMP version 3, Polifonia is currently setting out a survey for re-use of its Tool (software/application) and other resources, to identify and document properly the maturity level of developed Tools.

Concerning the impact beyond academia, Polifonia actively sought to present its results at public events (SONAR, Research night, EuropeanaTECH) and collaborated with artists and other communities. Its dissemination strategy does include social media, but also YouTube. From the beginning, Polifonia (partner Digital Paths) developed a visual language which supports the communication about the project. The ten Pilots all represent a certain combination of research and or information tasks, which is reflected in their colours, while the Icon's represents the main content.

⁵ <https://zenodo.org/communities/polifonia>

Figure 1: Overview about the Pilots with colour coding (from Peter van Kranenburg’s presentation January 19, 2024)

Figure 2: Illustration of the content/resources/problems behind the Pilots (taken from a presentation of Peter van Kranenburg, January 19, 2024)

This visual language has been embraced in all of the dissemination. The Polifonia project website is designed from an artistic point of view. The Polifonia Portal will complement the website by providing an interface to the content of Polifonia (resources now linked by semantic web technologies) for researchers as well as a wider audience interested in music and music history.

Example 2: Stakeholder Podiumkunst.net cooperation

During the second stakeholder meeting, a selected number of stakeholders were invited to work with the Polifonia project partners on components they are interested in re-using. One of these partners was Podiumkunst.net. Podiumkunst.net is a network organization that brings together collections of Dutch heritage organisations and performance arts in order to make these collections available to creators, researchers and enthusiasts. Like Polifonia, they build a knowledge graph to create these connections and foster reuse. During the Polifonia stakeholder meeting, we worked on aligning the Music Meta ontology with RDA - the ontology chosen by Podiumkunst.net. This turned out to be a rewarding effort and Music Meta has been able to complement the RDA model. An extensive report of this day and effort is available (Dutch only) on the Podiumkunst.net website.

“For the digital management and knowledge exchange within the cultural heritage sector, the connection between the Polifonia and Podiumkunst.net ontologies is a crucial step toward linking European digital music collections” quote by Monique in het Veld, project manager for Podiumkunst.net⁶

3. Policy recommendations

The policy recommendations highlight a number of issues, we order them around aspects of Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability and Reusability of both relevant datasets and developed tools and explore ways to address these issues at a policy level.⁷ The Polifonia project clearly displays the importance of these principles, and shows how these principles should not only guide the publication of scientific data, but also data from the cultural heritage sector which are increasingly also seen in their role also as research data (Chambers et al. 2023). In this policy brief, we do not replicate the work done by current projects and networks such as GO FAIR⁸, FAIRsFAIR⁹, or FAIR-Impact¹⁰. Instead, we will zoom in on a number of concrete issues we have faced in the Polifonia endeavour. This way, this report also complements the discourse around how to best implement FAIR with observations of concrete problems during implementation, and complements the last version of the DMP. The DMP answers the questions on FAIR by stating *what we have done*. The report is organised around identified *issues* and *recommendations*, detailing the *how we have done it*.

3.1 Findability

Issues

⁶<https://www.podiumkunst.net/nieuws/de-polifonia-stakeholdersdag-een-bruisende-ontmoetingsplaats-voor-digitaal-muziekbeheer/>

⁷ <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/>

⁸ <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/>

⁹ <https://www.fairsfair.eu>

¹⁰ <https://fair-impact.eu/>

In setting up an ecosystem which supports the discovery of non-trivial relations between objects of musical heritage across borders of countries, institutions and disciplines, the availability of datasets is crucial. Polifonia's work making an inventory (a dataset catalogue for such datasets) brought to light a number of issues. Metadata about datasets is not published centrally or consistently, which makes it difficult to find and therefore requires a lot of manual labour to gain insight into the available relevant datasets out there on the web. Once datasets have been found, it is hard to know what these datasets are about, and what their relationship is to musical heritage. Most dataset annotations and metadata are generic and do not cover specific subdomains of musical heritage. Also, it is often unclear what the source and provenance of a dataset are. This became particularly visible in the survey conducted by work package one (Guillotet-Nothmann et al. 2021), and the 'data stories' interviews conducted as part of the Research Data Management Plan (Admiraal et al. 2021).

This unclarity about the source and provenance is not only prevalent for datasets that contain metadata and content. The same goes for ontologies and vocabularies that have been developed to represent musical heritage information (Meroño Peñuela et al. 2021). Simply resorting to web search, dataset search and querying a public data repository such as Zenodo do not render satisfactory results. They provide little insight into what domains and questions ontologies cover, which datasets have been annotated with them and which knowledge graphs employ them.

Recommendations

1. Put in sufficient effort of publishing relevant subsets (available both for human and machine consumption)

Publishers of data should be made aware of their responsibility in publishing their datasets in such a way that these can easily be retrieved. Increasingly, machine readability (API's) and often Linked Data formats are required. Adhere to standards, and organise training how to produce data as knowledge graphs. Many cultural heritage institutions might publish their catalogue metadata, covering the entirety of a collection, but not bother with describing subsets of their catalogue related to, in our case, music. This means that the user of the data either has to be aware of relevant subsets and do the work of extracting the relevant subsets themselves from the full catalogue data, or that users might not be able to find this data at all. Providing the subset at the source means that expert curators familiar with the dataset can determine which resources are related to musical history and relevant tags can be attributed to a subset that are meaningful for expert users from the musical research community. Alternatively, example queries can be provided that return relevant subsets to users.

2. Use public data repositories

The same goes for research data and the ontologies developed by researchers to analyse the data. After having finished a journal publication or research project, the data and ontologies should be published in public data repositories, such as Zenodo or Kaggle, described in specific dataset

registry such as the domain-specific musoW registry¹¹, or deposited in national registries such as the Dutch DANS Data Station¹² and the Data Registry of the Dutch Digital Heritage Network.¹³ Datasets should be attributed with sufficient, accurate and fine-grained metadata for future users to be able to retrieve and reuse it. Protocols should be established that both heritage institutions and researchers adhere to in publishing their datasets and the use of standard vocabularies should be encouraged so that standardized terms can be used to query.

Example 3: The musoW registry

MusoW is a catalogue of musical resources available on the web realized with the idea to support teachers in music education, creative industries, historians, and musicologists in finding what they need. It is an example of a public data repository in which music-specific datasets on the web are registered.

Usually, scholars and creatives need to combine diverse resources (music scores, audiovisual materials, data) from digital music libraries and audiovisual archives. They need to identify valuable sources of information, find similarities or cross-references. Tech-savvy people want to access music data programmatically to develop their innovative projects. The research of good music sources is mostly done manually, reviewing tons of websites.

In musoW, Polifonia supports users in searching across hundreds of online resources, including digital libraries, archives, datasets, and related technologies.

3.2 Accessibility

Issues

Datasets, once found, exist in all kinds of distributions on the web. In their most basic form they exist as a data dump in (hopefully) a non-proprietary format. In more ideal situations it is published via an API or harvesting protocol such as OAI-PMH, or it's available on a SPARQL endpoint. However, the plethora of types of endpoints makes it harder to synchronize between these datasets.

Due to copyright a lot of musical heritage has limited (public) availability. This topic is further addressed in paragraph 2.5 Reusability below. But this is a reality in which researchers in this field function. It seems though that access for researchers to relevant datasets is often more restricted than necessary. There are all kinds of exceptions and agreements with copyright holders that allow datasets to be published in environments that require some sort of authentication. These datasets are hidden from plain sight and therefore harder to find.

¹¹ <https://projects.dharc.unibo.it/musow/>

¹² <https://dans.knaw.nl/nl/data-stations/social-sciences-and-humanities/>

¹³ <https://datasetregister.netwerkdigitaalerfgoed.nl/>

Recommendations

1. Use standardized distribution methods

Make sure that data is published in such a way that no proprietary tools or communication methods are needed, and where licenses allow it, are publicly accessible. When creating endpoints on datasets, try to conform to what is commonly used within a certain field to make these more accessible. Provide example queries that give people unfamiliar with the dataset ideas on how to search within the data and which kinds of questions can be answered based on the data. Alternatively, institutions can provide dashboards, visualisations of the data or create data stories to give (potential) users an insight into the dataset. Polifonia has developed a bespoke software solution to cope with the dissemination of datasets along with clear examples of usage and curated descriptions i.e. MELODY.¹⁴ Similar solutions are also available for single partners.¹⁵

2. If authentication is required, still focus on accessibility

If the material must be published under the condition of user authentication, try to connect to existing platforms that facilitate such access so that the material is available to as many existing users as possible right away. Make sure the availability of the dataset is publicly known, so that people that qualify for an account can find their way to them. The dataset metadata should be registered in relevant dataset registries (e.g. Dutch Heritage datasets in the NDE Dataset registry¹⁶ or European musical heritage datasets in musoW¹⁷), and the metadata describing the dataset should contain information on the degree to which and to whom it is accessible. Accounts to access these datasets should be easy to acquire for a broad range of researchers, not just from academics, but also for curators.

Example 4: Providing example queries on NISV SPARQL Endpoint

It may not always be possible, or desirable, to publish specific datasets for specific uses. Users of large datasets however may struggle to understand the data and the type of questions they can answer using that data. Providing a SPARQL endpoint with a user-friendly interface and example queries can go a long way in inspiring and informing users about the possibilities. The SPARQL endpoint of NISV¹⁸ for instance, provides many example queries. The queries can easily be adopted to cater to the users' needs. In the Polifonia project, sample queries were created for the full MOZ collection (concert collection) of NISV and subqueries were defined such as top 10 creators, all concerts and involved persons and standardised locations (enrichments made by aligning to Wikidata).

¹⁴ <https://projects.dharc.unibo.it/melody/>

¹⁵ In the Polifonia project, the Netherlands Institute for Sound & Vision created a dashboard for their concert collection: <https://data.beeldengeluid.nl/datasets/muziekopnamen-zendgemachtigden>

¹⁶ <https://datasetregister.netwerkdigitaalerfgoed.nl/>

¹⁷ <https://projects.dharc.unibo.it/musow/>

¹⁸ <https://cat.apis.beeldengeluid.nl/sparql>

3.3 Interoperability

Issues

In order to find meaningful connections between datasets there have to be sufficient ways in which to make these connections. Objects of musical heritage are varied, ranging from sheet music, audio recordings, performance registrations and musical instruments to contextual archival records such as letters and other documents. Added to that there are datasets that are extracted out of audio files and sheet music based on content analysis, such as melodic, harmonic and rhythmic patterns, either manually or by using algorithms. All this information often exists in separate datasets without exposing the relationships between them.

In order to perform analytical tasks across these datasets a lot of work goes into preparing the data, e.g. conforming it to a single data format or annotating it with standard vocabulary. This work is usually done once and then not published sustainably for future reuse. When new datasets are created based on existing datasets, the relationship between the two becomes unclear. Any changes in the original dataset are not transferred to any derivative or enriched datasets. This causes a messy landscape of partially overlapping datasets that can no longer be traced back to their source.

Next to datasets and ontologies, the Polifonia Research Ecosystem consists of a number of tools and technologies that will play an important role in answering the needs of relevant communities and stakeholders. Since it is a collaborative initiative, these technologies originate from a diverse range of partners. Coordinating the technical developments and resulting output components has been challenging. Typically, research outputs are scattered in different repositories, using different technologies (e.g. programming languages and frameworks). Integrating the systems under a single framework or technology constitutes a significant overhead for the project and usually results in assets that are hard to maintain and reuse after the end of the project.

Recommendations

1. Dynamic dataset metadata and documentation

To address these issues and subsequently increase interoperability, dataset descriptions should evolve over time, including information about how they relate to other datasets. Information that is too detailed to be captured in descriptive metadata fields should be documented. This documentation should include information about which datasets it has been linked to in the past and which methods were used in order to do so. It should also contain information about previous experiments that have been performed with the dataset as well as any publications that made use of these datasets.

2. Use persistent identifiers

A more radical and comprehensive way of preventing the messy landscape of datasets described above, but harder to implement, would be to adhere more radically to Linked Data standards. A distributed network in which datasets and data points within the data can be referenced using

persistent identifiers means that once connections are established, these can be sustainably managed, reused and expanded upon. Therefore, the use of persistent identifiers should be encouraged in libraries, archives and museums, but also in the research community. Persistent identifiers should be used at various levels, they can refer to collections, datasets, records, statements about records, descriptive terms, but also authors (e.g. ORCID's).¹⁹

3. Use shared ontologies and metadata formats

To make the process of linking the wide range of available datasets easier, the reuse of an interconnected network of ontologies that share alignments to other schemas and resources is fundamental. This is work that the project has contributed with the Polifonia Ontology Network [D2.2, [Article](#)]. The Polifonia Ontology Network (PON), a set of new ontologies formalising the semantics of music representation, metadata, annotation, analysis, mediums of performance (instruments), and historical sources (provenance). PON provides a modular backbone of music ontologies comprising 15 ontology modules that are organised thematically and hierarchically, to highlight their dependencies. At the bottom of the architecture lies our **Core** module (providing general-purpose elements of design, ODPs, and alignments) and the reused ontologies. Four foundational models provide interoperability across PON through their abstract design: Source, Instrument, Music Meta, and Music Representation. These are specialised and extended in the upper levels to add functionalities and contextualise specific domains. Central to the overarching goal of interconnecting music datasets from metadata information is the Music Meta ontology [[Article](#)], a rich and flexible semantic model to describe music metadata related to artists, compositions, performances, recordings, and links. Rather than attempting to provide a definitive solution to represent music metadata, our ontology has an abstract design allowing for specialisation and extendibility – depending on the particular music domain (genre/style/period, etc.), requirements and use cases.

4. Use shared vocabularies

Data can be described, tagged and annotated with terms from existing standard vocabularies. If all datasets were to use the same vocabularies to describe assets, this would of course be ideal. Often the choice for a particular standard vocabulary however is based on the vocabulary most commonly used in a specific sector or around a specific topic at a certain time. And once a choice for a specific vocabulary is made to describe items in a certain collection, it is unlikely that this will change. Creating alignments between vocabularies, where terms from one vocabulary are referenced in the terms of another vocabulary, makes seeing relations between datasets using those vocabularies much easier.

As an example, Music Meta is aligned to other key metadata ontologies in the music domain, including the Music Ontology, DOREMUS, and the schema of Wikidata describing musical information. In addition, the Polifonia team has collaborated with relevant partners in the Polifonia Stakeholder Network, and in particular with Podiumkunst.net and the Digital Music Observatory, to

¹⁹ For more detailed information about the use of PIDs we refer to the FREYA project funded under the Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme (<https://project-freya.eu/>).

create alignment with other models used in music sector (e.g RDA) and to evaluate its reuse and extension to describe other European Musical Heritage databases, respectively.

5. Encourage modular project outputs

Within Polifonia we follow a Knowledge Engineering approach to orchestrate the plethora of components developed or brought in by technical partners. We do this by means of an Ecosystem aimed at specifying the role and function of each asset (software, data, documentation, tutorials, requirements) in the context of the pilot use cases. The goal is to govern the diversity of assets without enforcing a single framework or technology, therefore reducing the effort of system integration. Instead, pilots have been developed by composing the various assets in pipelines, leveraging existing standards for interoperability, building on the tradition of Web technology specifications, Linked Data standards, Ontologies, Open Source software development, and good practices in the development of distributed systems.²⁰ Policy makers should encourage research projects to modularize project outputs, specify how they are used together to satisfy the project needs and document how stakeholders involved in developing end-user applications can reuse them beyond the scope of the project. The Polifonia Ecosystem can constitute a proof of concept of a novel approach to orchestrating project outputs and maximising their quality in terms of software and data engineering, and reduce the risks of the assets degrading after the end of the project. The methods and technologies developed are available for reuse by future EU projects in the Research Ecosystem Framework (REECO).²¹

²⁰ More on this methodology can be found in Daga, E. et al., Polifonia Deliverable 1.3: Pilots development - collaborative methodology and tools (2021).

²¹ REECO <http://github.com/reeco-framework>

3.4 Reusability

Issues

One of the most pressing matters within the field of research into musical heritage is the issue of copyright. Copyright can present severe limitations on what information a user is able to find online and if they do find it, what they are able to do with this data in their analysis. Especially when analysing collections at scale, using digital methods, it simply becomes too expensive to buy licenses for large amounts of copyright-protected material from publishers or copyright organisations.

One of the first issues that we run into is the lack of license information provided with music-related datasets. This lack of clarity almost necessarily means that by default copyright protection is assumed and therefore the data cannot be used. Digital music files (sheet music, audio files, etc.) are themselves subject to copyright and related rights like the executive rights of performing musicians. The purpose of these laws is to make sure that creators can protect their creative works against theft and receive proper remuneration. As a consequence, research activities may be limited because of it as well. Music recordings, lyrics and sheet music may not be freely available on the web. And if the music is available, analysis of such files might be subject to copyright law. There is a grey area in the degree to which content analysis of music, and forthcoming metadata is a copy or derivative of the original work, and therefore subject to copyright law.

Recommendations

1. Explore industry-research collaborations

Music publishers should be encouraged to support researchers by allowing access to their catalogues. Schemes of Return on Investment (ROI) should be analysed and identified to establish mutual benefits for industry, research and heritage. Polifonia for instance is committed to publishing the results of our analysis as open data (following the FAIR principles here described). We always link to the original source (e.g. the owner of recorded musical work) and share the results with the data owner. This can help them to exploit these analyses, for instance in promoting their music, making better recommendations and understanding their own ties to music culture and history. Owners of data can thus become early adopters of innovative technology to reach relevant audiences. It is important to note though that collaborations between research and industry do not solve all issues because not every type of research renders outcomes useful to the industry.

2. Provide clear copyright information in dataset descriptions

Copyright information should be clearly stated in dataset descriptions. This information concerns both copyright on the dataset itself, as well as the assets it contains. In describing copyright status it is most useful to use existing standards and machine-readable statements (such as Creative Commons and Rightsstatements.org). In attributing licenses, owners of data should be aware of the restrictions their chosen license poses for users of the data. In general licenses will determine the degree to which users can share and adapt, but also whether they have to attribute (mention

the owner of the dataset) and share their own adaptations of the dataset under the same license (share alike). It is easily underestimated how restrictive a certain license can be. For instance, having to attribute the owner of the datasets makes it very cumbersome for third parties to reuse the data as Linked Data. This is why for example Europeana has chosen the Creative Commons CC0 license.

Research projects that are publicly funded should embrace open licensing as a default mode of work in order for the results to be as widely available to the public as possible, and in addition to allow researchers to build on the work that has already been done. The DL2.6 Ontology of licencing, ownership and conditions of use (V1.0) showed how diverse the licence landscape is, and that even if a licence is there, it might not be machine readable. Polifonia has created a knowledge graph for licences, which is basically a W3C standard of how to annotate (Linked Data) licences. In the course of this work, the metadata field of the musoW catalogue was enriched.

3. Invest resources towards investigation of copyright status of existing collections

Heritage institutions and other collection holders should invest time and resources into exploring the degree to which their collections are available in the public domain. The knowledge in the Polifonia knowledge graph has the potential to contribute to this exploration. If works can be linked to sources containing the death date of authors (composers), material can confidently be published in the public domain if the copyright has expired.

In addition, this research can provide a clearer picture of who rights holders are and agreements can be made with them for access, even if just for educational and research purposes. Institutions should be made aware of exceptions under copyright law that they can benefit from in providing access to their collections.

Finally, it is also worthwhile exploring the possibilities for extracting information out of music-related collections and the degree to which this derivative information is exempt from copyright law.

4. Define template agreements

Define template agreements that can be used by European research project consortia to approach publishers and other rights holders. These agreements would address intellectual property issues, publishing/sharing limitations, allowed use, etc. Each European project can adjust these templates according to their needs, but in this way the main effort of establishing the terms is done once and can then be replicated.

5. Clarify the conditions under which Text and Data mining is allowed

If music data is published online and a researcher can rightfully access this music, analyzing the data to discover patterns and relations can be allowed without previous consent from rights holders. In Europe, however, there are still some legal uncertainties concerning the treatment of TDM practices under EU and national laws that potentially inhibit the development of TDM. Although mining data for knowledge discovery is allowed if a researcher has legal access, TDM often requires a step to copy the data, which in many cases requires specific authorization (Rosati

2018).

Although some European countries have adopted specific TDM exceptions, the conditions under which TDM is allowed differ and are not yet clarified. In order to foster a functioning European music research ecosystem, countries need to coordinate their EU and national copyright laws.

Example 5: Europeana Licensing Framework and Guidelines

Europeana shows that large scale open access to heritage objects and their metadata is possible and has considerable experience in dealing with the many issues that come up in convincing stakeholders to make their data available under open licenses.

In the Europeana Licensing Framework a clear distinction is being made between metadata and the contents that are being described by the metadata. The metadata itself must be available to Europeana under the CC0 license, however, data providers can decide themselves how rich the metadata they provide to Europeana should be. This allows data providers to keep certain types of metadata to themselves with the exception of some mandatory metadata fields. Where the objects described are in the Public Domain, drawing on the Europeana Public Domain Charter²² the Europeana Licensing Framework requires that data providers label digital objects that are in the public domain as such by applying the Public Domain Mark to them. To promote responsible re-use of public domain works that includes attribution for institutions that have invested in preserving, digitizing and making them available, Europeana has developed Usage Guidelines²³ for Public Domain works.

²² <https://www.europeana.eu/en/rights/public-domain-charter>

²³ <https://www.europeana.eu/en/rights/usage-guidelines-for-metadata>

4. Conclusions

In conclusion, this deliverable described the most important results from the Polifonia project, and offered recommendations to policy makers for navigating the complexities of European musical heritage engagement and management. Rooted in the foundational principles of FAIR—Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable—these recommendations can guide policymakers across diverse organizations.

The components such as the Polifonia Ecosystem, Polifonia Ontology Network and Polifonia Web Portal collectively represent the project's robust approach to data management, semantic web technologies, and user accessibility, providing a comprehensive infrastructure for engaging with European musical heritage.

The governance principles outlined reflect a commitment to good open science practices, with the Polifonia consortium uniquely comprising not only research institutions but also key cultural heritage organizations. Also, the creation of the stakeholder network added to the lasting impact of the project. This collaborative structure has facilitated the convergence of data curation practices, enriching metadata and increased potential for reuse. The project's emphasis on interdisciplinary collaboration, knowledge dissemination at public events, collaboration with artists, and a well-thought-out impact strategy showcases a holistic approach to ensuring that the project's outcomes transcend academic spheres and resonate in broader societal contexts.

As Polifonia delivers its final policy brief, it not only reflects on the journey of the project but also seeks to impart valuable lessons and insights for the benefit of future projects and policy makers in the dynamic landscape of cultural heritage engagement.

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